

DAMAGE EVALUATION OF FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE BY HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT

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1 Introduction

Concrete structure suffers damage by blast wave if explosion occurs. Additionally, destroy surrounding facilities because destroying concrete and metal fragments disperse at the speed of hundreds *m/s*, and there are instances that generate secondary damage in equipment with a person.

And projectiles or fragments generate localized effect characterized by penetration or perforation, spalling scabbing, as well as more widespread crack propagation[1].

To impact resistance performance of concrete, several investigations by such as Zhang et al.[1], Vossoughi et al.[2], Li et al.[3], Yankelevsky[4] and Beppu et al.[5] have conducted studies on the impact behavior of concrete by high-velocity impact.

According to previous studies[1-5], reported that relation on the concrete performance of compressive strength, tensile strength and strain, thickness for impact resistance performance.

Therefore, in this study, presents results from an experimental study on the impact resistance of fiber reinforced concrete with fiber types by high velocity steel projectile test. The effects of the compressive and tensile strength of the concrete, and the performance of reinforcement types of the concrete are discussed.

2 Experimental Plan and Methods

2.1 Materials and mixture program

The mix proportions of the fiber reinforced concrete are shown in Table 1. The water/binder ratio(W/B) was 0.4 and unit weight of the binder was 1,129kg/m³. Details pertaining the type and properties of the materials are shown in Table 2.

2.2 Experimental setup

All specimens subjected to impact tests had a common size of 100×100mm and a thickness of 10mm. The specimens for a compressive, tensile and bending strength test at 28days, after removal from the molds at 1 day, were cured in water at 20±3°C until an age of 27days.

Table 1. Mix proportions of concrete

Mix ID ¹⁾	W/B	Water (kg/m ³)	Cement (kg/m ³)	FA ²⁾ (kg/m ³)	Sand (kg/m ³)	Fiber ³⁾ (kg/m ³)
Plain	0.4	452	960	169	395	-
PVA	0.4	452	960	169	395	25.5
PE	0.4	452	960	169	395	18.6
STF	0.4	452	960	169	395	153.9
PVA-S ⁴⁾	0.4	452	960	169	395	12.9+77.7
PE-S ⁴⁾	0.4	452	960	169	395	9.4+77.7

1) PVA : polyvinyl alcohol, PE : polyethylene, STF : steel fiber, PVA-S : PVA+STF, PE-S : PE+STF

2) FA : Fly-ash

3) Fiber content : 2vol. %

4) Fiber content ratio : PVA:STF, PE:STF 1:1

Table 2. Materials

Materials	Physical and chemical properties
Cement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ordinary Portland cement, ▪ Density : 3.15g/cm³ / Fineness : 3,770cm²/g
Fly-ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Density : 2.30g/cm³ / Fineness : 3,228cm²/g
Sand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Silica sand No.7 / Density : 2.64g/cm³ ▪ Absorption ratio : 0.38%
PVA fiber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Density : 1.30g/cm³ ▪ Tensile strength : 1,300MPa ▪ Length : 12mm / Diameter : 40 μm
PE fiber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Density : 0.95g/cm³ ▪ Tensile strength : 2,700MPa ▪ Length : 15mm / Diameter : 12 μm
Steel fiber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Density : 7.85g/cm³ ▪ Tensile strength : 1,140MPa ▪ Length : 50.9mm / Diameter : 700 μm
Super-plasticizer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Polycarboxylic acid type

Fig. 1. Schematic graph of the impact test set-up

(a) Non failure (b) Cratering (c) Spalling (d) Perforation
Fig.2. Failure modes of local damage

Fig.3. Example of damage mapping on specimen

Fig.4. Damage evaluation of cratering and spalling

2.3 Evaluation method of impact testing

The experimental arrangement for projectile impact tests is shown in Fig. 1. This system can launch

projectile with the velocity of $\sim 370\text{m/s}$. And steel projectile with a diameter of 4mm were used.

The local damage of concrete specimens is commonly classified into four modes, non failure, cratering, spalling and perforation as shown in Fig. 2. The extent of the damage to each specimen was quantified graphically by mapping the craters on the front and back sides and comparing the crater area, A_1 , to the total area, $A_1 + A_2$. This is demonstrated in Fig. 3. The percent of surside damage was calculated by $100\% \times A_2/(A_1 + A_2)$. And damage evaluation of cratering and spalling are shown in Fig. 4.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Test results of engineering properties

Fig. 5, Table 3 summarize the test results of engineering properties for 6 concrete mixtures with fiber reinforcement type at age 28days.

Fig.5. Test results of specimen strength

Table 3. Test results of engineering properties

ID	Ave. compressive strength (N/mm ²)	Ave. tensile strength (N/mm ²)	Ave. tensile strain (%)	Ave. bending strength (N/mm ²)	Ave. bending length (mm)
Plain	43.7	1.71	0.05	4.13	0.14
PVA	28.5	3.96	6.33	24.66	2.35
PE	27.9	3.61	4.01	30.74	4.24
STF	34.7	3.92	2.27	33.15	2.78
PVA-S	35.8	6.34	2.12	29.08	1.68
PE-S	36.7	8.88	2.87	29.37	3.16

Compressive strength of fiber reinforced concrete specimen was lower than it of Plain specimen. However tensile and bending strength of fiber reinforced concrete specimen was higher than it of Plain specimen.

3.2 Test results of impact resistance

The local damage of Plain specimen and fiber reinforced concrete specimen are shown in Table 4, respectively. The cross-sections images in these figures show perpendicular sections to support direction.

The projectile impact velocity ranged from 350 to 363m/s. PE, PVA-S and PE-S specimen was shown cratering condition, and reduced the spalling of concrete by fiber reinforcement.

The results of surside damage of front and back sides are shown in Fig. 6. In case of Plain specimen, superficial damage was occurred more 6.9% in back side than front side. Thus, In case of PE, PVA-S and PE-S specimen, superficial damage was reduced and the destruction of front side was bigger than Back side In contrast with Plain specimen.

Table 4. Damage of specimens with reinforcement type after test

Mix	(a) Plain	(b) PVA
Results		
side	front back	front back
Failure mode	Spalling	Spalling
Mix	(c) PE	(d) STF
Results		
side	front back	front back
Failure mode	Cratering	Spalling
Mix	(e) PVA-S	(f) PE-S
Results		
Side	front back	front back
Failure mode	Cratering	Cratering

Fig.6. Surside damage of front and back sides of specimens

Fig.7. Correlation of back side damage and compressive strength of specimens

Fig.8. Correlation of back side damage and tensile strength of specimens

Fig.9. Correlation of back side damage and bending strength of specimens

The Correlation of superficial damage and compressive, tensile and bending strength of specimen by impact are shown in Fig. 7, 8, 9. The more tensile and bending strength higher, the less superficial damage of back side. And compressive strength have no direct effect on impact resistance performance.

3.3 Test results of AUTODYN simulation

Fig.10. Numerical model

Fig.11. The RHT constitutive model used for concrete[6]

Fig.12. Damage results of AUTODYN simulation of specimens

In order to reproduce the local damage, numerical simulations have been performed by using a general purpose hydrocode AUTODYN. In Fig. 10, a numerical analysis is shown in the two dimensional axisymmetric model. Four-node quadrilateral elements are applied to the concrete specimen and the projectile. The concrete specimen consists of 16,000 elements, and size of each element is 2 mm × 2 mm. The projectile consists of 512 elements.

In the numerical analyses, the RHT model was used, and the model, which consists of three yield surfaces, as shown in Fig. 11.

Damage and strain results of AUTODYN simulation of specimens is illustrated in Fig. 12~18. Damage and strain of fiber reinforced concrete specimen was lower than it of Plain specimen.

Fig.13. Strain histories by simulation of Plain specimen

Fig.16. Strain histories by simulation of STF specimen

Fig.14. Strain histories by simulation of PVA specimen

Fig.17. Strain histories by simulation of PVA-S specimen

Fig.15. Strain histories by simulation of PE specimen

Fig.18. Strain histories by simulation of PE-S specimen

4 Conclusions

In the present work, the effectiveness of fiber reinforcement on the impact resistance performance of concrete specimen has been investigated. Tensile and bending strength of fiber reinforced concrete specimen was higher than it of Plain specimen and such as the fiber reinforced concrete was more decrease back side damage. Fiber reinforced concrete has higher impact resistance than plain specimen. And the effect of fiber reinforcement in terms of enhancing the mechanical properties of brittle cementitious composites arises from load transfer from the brittle matrix to the fibers and the bridging effect of the fibers across cracks propagating in the matrix. Finally, the impact resistance of specimens was calculated from viewpoint of fracture mode by AUTODYN and it was concluded that fiber reinforced concrete improve the impact resistance performance.

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